

A HIGH THROUGHPUT WELL PLATE SYSTEM WITH VARIED OXYGEN LEVELS TO SIMULATE THE INTERVERTEBRAL DISC MICROENVIRONMENT

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INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in cell-based therapies aim to regenerate the intervertebral disc (IVD) through matrix deposition and restoration of disc height [1]. Many studies have failed to consider the distinct microenvironment of the IVD which plays a key role in the function and survival of the cells [2, 3]. As this microenvironment is specific to each individual, it undoubtedly impacts clinical outcomes.

The aim of this work is to elucidate the effects of different nutrient microenvironments and to ultimately design and tailor cell therapies to optimise outcomes on an individual basis. The microenvironment of the human IVD will be profiled assessing oxygen, glucose and pH levels as well as quantities of both regenerative and inflammatory cytokines. Through in silico modelling and predictive screening the number of cells delivered could be optimised such that the microenvironment of the IVD is not exacerbated resulting in cell death. As a first step towards this goal, we aim to generate multiple oxygen microenvironments across a single 24 well plate, in which the response of IVD cells can be assessed. Clinically relevant oxygen concentrations ranging from 1-10% will be modelled and experimentally validated using nucleus pulposus and annulus fibrosus derived cells.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In silico modelling was performed using COMSOL 5.6 multiphysics software to assess the diffusion of oxygen within a 24 well plate. The 24 well plate was modelled to contain inserts with inner cylindrical columns of varying diameters (Figure 1 b) to alter the surface area exposed to the oxygen within the incubator (11% oxygen). Each column of 4 wells within the plate was taken as a group, with 6 groups in total. The volume of media is kept constant in each well (1235 μ l) to minimise differences between glucose and lactate gradients. This results in a range of media heights within the cylindrical channels, altering the length of the diffusion paths in each group (Figure 1 g). This in turn alters the oxygen gradients within each group.

Oxygen concentration was the primary focus, with coupled modelling also performed for glucose and lactate levels to ensure they remained relatively stable. Modelling was based on a dilute species transport, with initial concentrations of 11% oxygen, 5.5mM glucose and 1.4mM lactate. Cellular reactions were assigned to hydrogel discs of 6mm diameter and 2 mm height at a cell density of 4 million cells/ml. Analysis was performed for 7 days with probes used to monitor the average concentration of each species.

RESULTS

Results of the in-silico modelling are outlined in figure 1. Concentrations of oxygen were obtained between 1 – 10 % with a plateau observed after 2 days. The maximum reduction in glucose concentration at 0.45mM occurred in the lowest oxygen well. Similarly, this well had the greatest increase in lactate at 0.9mM.

Figure 1 Effect of well geometry on concentration of oxygen, glucose and lactate. a) Isometric view of plate. b) XY plane highlighting plate geometry. c) Contour plot of oxygen concentrations (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10% from left to right). d)–f) Graph of oxygen, glucose and lactate concentrations respectively. g) Plate geometry and resulting oxygen concentrations.

DISCUSSION & FUTURE WORK

The in-silico modelling predicts a range of oxygen microenvironments can be achieved on a single 24 well plate. However, further experimental validation is required. This will be performed using a Presens SDR SensorDish reader to monitor the oxygen concentrations in the well over a 7-day period. It is envisaged that this validation will enable us to analyse the effect of multiple microenvironments on the behaviour of IVD cells in parallel.

REFERENCES

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